

ETHER

Development ecosystem for the rapid release of application-tailored storage systems

Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions

Call: H2020-MSCA-IF-2019

Call topic: Individual Fellowships

Project start: 1st May 2020

Project duration: 24 Months

D1.2: Infer from systems primitives to create systems APIs. (Project Deliverables)

Executive summary

This document provides a set of basic APIs required for the development of a storage system. It provides technological aspects that include interaction with storage endpoints (e.g, block devices, filesystems, cloud), data processing services (e.g, compress, strip, erasure coding), and coordination services (e.g, metadata lookup, distributed sync).

Deliverable owner: Fotios Nikolaidis

Project funded by the European Commission within Horizon 2020
Dissemination Level

PU	Public	PU
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	–
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	–
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	–

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 894204

Deliverable Information

Document administrative information	
Project acronym:	ETHER
Grant Agreement:	894204
Deliverable number:	D1.2
Deliverable full title:	Infer from systems primitives to create systems APIs.
Deliverable short title:	System APIs
Document identifier:	ETHER-D1.2-System APIs-v1.1-submitted
Individual Fellow:	Fotios Nikolaidis
Report version:	v1.1
Report submission date:	April 5, 2022
Dissemination level:	PU
Nature:	Deliverable for Ether Implementation
Lead author(s):	Fotios Nikolaidis
Co-author(s):	Manolis Marazakis, Angelos Bilas
Status:	submitted

Change log

Date	Version number	Author/Editor	Summary of changes made
24/03/2022	v1.1	Fotios Nikolaidis	Final report
10/01/2021	v1.0	Fotios Nikolaidis	Draft report template

Table of Contents

1. INTRODUCTION	4
2. PROGRAMMABLE VIRTUAL STORAGE DEVICES	4
2.1 APPROACH	4
2.2 API	5
2.2.1 Channels	5
2.2.2 Streams	6
2.2.3 Futures	6
2.2.4 Items	6
3. PROGRAMMABLE I/O PROCESSORS	6
3.1 API	7
3.1.1 Processing kernels.....	8
3.1.2 State Management.....	8
3.1.3 Network Ports.....	8
3.1.4 Federated Network Discovery	9
4. PROGRAMMABLE COORDINATORS	9
4.1 APPROACH	9
4.1.1 Metadata Catalog.....	10
4.1.2 Distributed Synchronization	10
4.2 API	11
4.2.1 Update Transaction	11
4.2.2 View Transactions	11
4.3 RECORD MASKING	11

List of abbreviations

EC	European Commission
DoA	Description of Action
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DMP	Data Management Plan

1 Introduction

In the deliverable D1.1 of the Ether project, we collected, analyzed, and decomposed established storage systems to discover patterns and reveal cross-cutting principles that underpin their functionality. We summarized our findings on an 'atlas' of functionalities that collectively constitute a storage system. Among them, we identified:

- Data Storage Architectures
- In-transit Processing
- I/O Optimizations
- Data Placement Policies
- Fault-Tolerance Strategies
- Replication Models
- Node Discovery Approaches
- Leader Election Protocols
- Deployment Techniques

In this deliverable, we provide a set of coherent APIs that allow us to create virtual classes of these functionalities so that particular implementations can be easily swapped on and of. The overall vision is to provide a framework that will implement minimally constraining flow mechanisms, leaving a bunch of strategically predefined blanks for developers to fill out with virtual functions that better fit their applications.

2 Programmable Virtual Storage Devices

When an application wants to transfer data to and from a data store, it must incorporate the API for that data store in its source code. That means the application must also know the constraints, semantics, synchronization of communication, and the request/reply syntax.

For many decades, the POSIX filesystems were the standard interface for storing data. It defined a programming model to ensure application portability across different implementations of POSIX-compliant filesystems. However, POSIX filesystems were deprecated by the emerging Cloud Storage world. Albeit the Amazon S3 API seems to dominate, other major vendors like Microsoft Azure and Google Cloud Storage are also trying to promote their solutions and APIs. Subsequently, if applications incorporate vendor-specific API, they are bound to that vendor. To avoid vendor-lock, Multi-cloud connectors such as libcloud (Libcloud, 2020) for Python, jclouds (jclouds, 2020) for Java, and Stow (Stow, 2020) for Golang provide a unified API with the "lowest common denominator" (Petcu, Craciun, & Rak, 2011; Shalom, 2020) of features available in all platforms. Under the hood, connectors translate the unified API calls to vendor-specific calls. The drawback is they hide vendor-specific capabilities from applications. Examples include asynchronous operations, notifications, configuration management, monitoring, and policies. The pitfall is that even a unified API does not guarantee that the underlying storage system will exhibit identical behaviours. A potential solution would be for applications to integrate code paths for every support vendor, but such an approach would significantly complicate the development and maintenance effort.

2.1 Approach

In our design, the *Devices* prove a virtualization layer that enables developers not only to swap on and off "plugins", but rather to combine multiple plugins into a single runtime drive. Such drivers retain access

to all the robust features and rich sets of services the cloud offers and, at the same time, provide an integrated means for applications to access diverse storage platforms, i.g., achieve portability.

This strategy allows us to achieve different I/O characteristics over the same storage devices or cloud platform. For instance, if we have a write-intensive application and a read-intensive application operating over the same physical disk, we can create two virtual devices over that disk, with each virtual counterpart featuring different properties. In the case of write-intensive applications, we can create a virtual device that aggregates requests before flushing them to the physical device. In the case of read-intensive applications, we can create another virtual device with prefetching and caching capabilities. Eventually, these virtual devices can be used to normalize data stores, tune I/O handling to the expected workload, and harness performance benefits by moving functionality closer to the data.

2.2 API

As shown in Table 1, the *Device* API is built around the concept of *Channels* and *Streams*. The *Channels* are cross-layer constructs that appear to clients as different and isolated instances of the *Driver*. Clients can use channels to avoid dealing with complex locking. The *Streams* are asynchronous channel operations for transferring sequences of bytes with arbitrary lengths. Every *Stream* is associated with an *Item*; a token (future) to represent the results of asynchronous *Streams*. When the channel closes, the *Item* is populated with all the necessary information to reconstruct the original data.

2.2.1 Channels

Before starting transferring data to and from the *Device*, the clients must establish an end-to-end channel with it. The channel creation is synchronous. Every layer that receives the creation request initializes a local channel and forwards the request down the stack. The process continues until the request reaches the *Connector*.

When this happens, the *Connectors* are responsible for interacting with the actual storage backend, creating a new collection on the backend, replies the request with the collection identifier. Depending on the backend, the collection can be a directory (for filesystems), a bucket (for object storage), or a key prefix (for key/value stores). Once the collection is created, the reply propagates the stack upwards, with every layer linking its local channel to the channel of its lower layer. Once the reply reaches the client, a cross-layer channel is established, identified by the collection identifier.

Channels are also bound with cancellation contexts which carry deadlines, cancellation signals and other request-scoped values across API boundaries and between processes (Doxsey, 2016). The contexts are triggered explicitly (e.g., abort a handler-level operation) or implicitly (e.g., timeout). The channel gracefully terminates its streams and removes the written object from the backend when this happens.

- **Grouping:** In case of crash or abort, we must remove the partially written to reclaim the storage space. Crash handling mechanisms such as Journalling or distributed transactions maintain a persisted log of intentions and affected location so to recover the crash. Tracking every single stream requires those logs to be continuously updated. For journalling, that translates to multiple I/O to the disk, and for the distributed transactions, multiple round-trips over the network. Exploiting that a channel directs all of its streams into the same collection, it suffices to know the collection identifier.
- **Synchronization:** The convention is that error handling goes to the level of the channel, not to the level of the individual stream. As a result, the state of the streams can be in flux until the channel closes. For example, even if one stream is successful, the channel will remove the persisted data if another stream in the channel fails to persist. That is known as the Release consistency model. A possible analogy is that of a revision control system. The channels are like branches, streams

like commits to the local branch, and channel closing is like pushing the local branch to a remote server. Only after the `commit()` is issued other clients can access the data.

2.2.2 Streams

Streaming pipes provide an encapsulation that crosses the various layers with zero-copy capabilities, i.e., avoids copying data from one layer to another. Streams gracefully close on End Of File (EOF). Streams are categorized into i) explicit user-initiated streams, transferring data from a client to the *Device*, and ii) implicit module-initiated streams, transferring data from one layer to another. The user-initiated stream may not be reflected directly into the physical device. For example, a buffering layer will aggregate multi user-initiated streams into a single module-initiated stream flushed to the physical device to optimize the I/O. Equally, a chunking layer will split a single user-initiated stream into multiple module-initiated streams to comply with the maximum supported chunk of the backend.

2.2.3 Futures

Central to the device API is the concept of a deferred or future. It is a holder for metadata whose value is still unknown because the I/O phase has not been completed yet (Liskov & Shrira, 1988). Futures can be passed around like regular objects that will block when asked for their value. This abstraction allows the state of a channel to be in flux for as long as the channel remains open but guarantee that the stream metadata will appear in the correct issue-order when the channel closes. For implementing a future, every handler embeds a lookup table for matching the (incoming) parent to the (outgoing) children's requests. When a caller submits a request, the callee immediately replies with a *future* that points to an index within a metadata lookup. The assigned index is incremental and represents the invocation order of the parent request. It can be regarded as a "token" or the caller to later retrieve the (sub)stream metadata from that lookup. Futures permit the *caller* to progress with its other tasks without stopping to wait for the data transfer to complete.

2.2.4 Items

An *Item* structure represents the metadata of a stream operation; it is a logical file pointing to data spread across various Cloud storage providers, containing all the necessary information to reconstruct the data of a stream. Its format is "collection::[]objec ::[]offset", where the [] symbol denote a list. The collection represents the group to which the channel was writing its data. The objects represent information about contiguous chunks written on the persisted storage in a single Connector operation. If the chunks are not separate elements on the backend but are part of a larger blob, the offset shows the chunk location within that blob.

By default, the *Device* only return *Items* serialized in JSON packets. These *Items* may be forwarded directly to the clients, which are responsible for the management or be forwarded to a metadata lookup service provided by the *Coordinator*.

3 Programmable I/O Processors

It is a rather straightforward process for a client to transfer data from and to a *Device*. Where it gets significantly more complicated is when a client needs to leverage more than one *Devices* simultaneously. Some of the reasons may include performance (i.e, strip data to multiple *Devices*), fault-tolerance (i.e, replicate data to multiple *Devices*), or privacy (i.e, encrypt and spread data across multiple *Devices*).

One way to perform these functions is to incorporate the respective logic into the source code of the client application. Unfortunately, parallel programming is tricky for thread execution, bridging (e.g.,

Device API	Return Value	Comment
Upstream(Name)	(Channel, error)	New upstream channel
Put(Channel, io.Reader)	(Future, error)	New write stream
Close(Channel)	(error)	Flush, close channel
Metadata([]Future)	map[Future]Item	Return items
Downstream(Name, Item)	(Channel, error)	Create channel
Get(Channel, io.Writer)	(Future, error)	New read stream
Scan()	([]string, []Item, error)	Index external data-store contents
Structure	Fields	
Channel	(Collection, Mode, Context)	Isolated view of the driver
Stream	(Index, Parent, Mode)	Asynchronous Data transfer
Item	(Off, Size, ID, Chain []Item)	Metadata for the data transfer

Table 1: Stackable API implemented by the translators and the connector. Remove(), Info() and other calls are emitted for abbreviation.

buffering), and synchronization for thread safety. Frameworks and languages such as M I-IO library (Hildebrand & Nisar, 2009) or Chapel (Sidelnik, Maleki, Chamberlain, Garzarán, & Padua, 2012) can address some of the above but have a steep learning curve and therefore are not suitable for general use. Moreover, every new application must reimplement the same codepaths.

In our approach, we introduce the *I/O Processor* as an intermediate that allows the injection and execution of data processing routines without the burden of systems programming. More specifically, the *I/O Processor* provides a declarative language the developers can model the desired I/O path as a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) of processing modules.

Interposing between the application the *Devices*, the *I/O Processors* make it possible to apply post-processing routines to application output, transparently to the application. Suitable tasks include those that reduce data without loss of scientific validity (e.g., compression, deduplication), improve information content (e.g., add simulation timestamps), generate metadata (e.g., indexing), or perform lightweight analysis for visualization dashboards.

3.1 API

The *Processor's* API adheres to a visual programming paradigm called flow-based programming (FBP) (Morrison, 1978). FBP views an application not as a single sequential process with discrete start and finish points in time but as a *Network* of asynchronous “black box” processes. FBP focuses on the application data and the applied transformations to produce the desired output.

The major characteristics of Flow-based programming paradigm are (NoFlow, 2020) :

- Unified approach in software development from domain analysis to coding. Start with diagrams and data flows and continue the structural breakdown until the processing algorithms. Essentially it maps hardware engineering practices to software development
- Concurrency comes by design, not by purpose. Graph nodes run in parallel and share their state by exchanging messages. FBP applications run in less elapsed time than conventional programs and make optimal use of all the processors on a machine, with no special programming required to achieve this.

3.1.1 Processing kernels

The *Kernels* are fundamental event-driven processing components. They communicate using fixed-capacity connections that convey structured data chunks, called “Information Packets” (IP). Connections are attached to a kernel through a port; an agreed name between the kernel and the graph definition. The separate definition of connection minimizes kernel interdependence and skips the need to integrate a routing table within the kernel scope. Kernel “multiplex” incoming requests, passing each parent request on to one (processor/compress), some (processor/stripe), or all (processor/mirror) of the output ports. In case multiple outputs connect to a single input, the packets arrive in FIFO order. An output port can connect only to one input port; otherwise, the behaviour is undetermined. Both input and output ports can be scalar or array-type (e.g., for stripping). The number of ports per kernel is not limited, but keeping them a few to avoid cohesion and consistency issues is recommended.

Kernels must include three public fields in their structs: “Ingress”, “Egress”, and “Runtime”. Given those fields, the *Processor*’s scheduler automatically registers the kernel (i.e., fixing pointers) to the *Processor* without further involvement from the developer.

3.1.2 State Management

The I/O process is bidirectional, designed to support both read and write operations. The direction from clients to the *Devices* is called upstream, and the direction from *Devices* to clients is called downstream. For the client to interpret the data correctly, the downstream must inverse the transformations that occurred in the upstream. If the kernels participating in the upstream are stateful, their state on the upstream is also needed to reconstruct the original data. To achieve that, the *Processor* provides an environmental variable for *kernels* to store and load their state in a key-value manner.

3.1.3 Network Ports

The *Network* ports are virtual mappings for streaming data from external processes to the *Network* (collection of running *Kernels*). Ports are generally thought to be the boundaries that hide the structure of the internal *Network* from the outer world. The syntax for declaring a *Network* input port is as follows:

```
network.MapInPort("kernelName", func([]string), func(<-chan error) error)
```

The first argument is the kernel’s name to which the incoming traffic will be directed. The second argument is a callback function used to resolve compatibility issues during the linking. The third argument is a callback for deciding the returned error code of the *Network* based on the outcome of the output ports. In general, all the outputs must be written successfully before declaring the top-level operation successful. However, this is not always the case. For example, in “at least” replications schemes, the operation is successful when K out of N outputs ($k \leq N$) is written successfully. In such schemes, the operation can continue even in the presence of a limited number of errors, reducing the overhead of going into the recovery process. Further, it allows to acknowledge the operation faster and still be confident about the resiliency guarantees.

The syntax for declaring a *Network* output port is a bit different:

```
network.MapOutPort("processName", new(Context), ...requirements)
```

The first argument is the name of the kernel whose output will forward the outgoing traffic. The second argument is a Context, which carries deadlines, cancellation signals, and other request-scoped values across API boundaries and between processes. The context addresses the problem of indefinite blocking when the network connection between two components is lost. Instead, the *Processor*’s contexts are

associated with a timeout, which must be periodically renewed. If the timeout expires while waiting for a blocking connection, the context is automatically cancelled, and the cancellation propagates to the rest of the stack.

The third argument denotes the requirements for connecting to another entity. The tradeoff for relaxed security is the ability to pass hints to the other edge. Hints can be advisory to avoid implementing the same functionality twice on different layers (e.g., deduplication) or mandatory and denote a functional requirement that cannot be missing without jeopardizing application correctness (e.g., encryption). Hints are also useful in the *Device* selection process.

The corresponding client-side calls for binding an external process to the *Network*'s input and output ports are: `SetInPort()` and `SetOutPort()`.

3.1.4 Federated Network Discovery

To support atomic operation, it is necessary to resolve the number of affected *Devices* deterministically. For *Processors* whose outputs are linked directly to *Devices* this is straightforward. Affected devices are those connected to the *Network* ports. It is not trivial, though, when multiple *Processors* are combined to form a *Federated Composite Network*. That is because *Processors* can link in variable and dynamic ways, and there is no global graph to describe the structure of the *Composite Network*. For example, a client sends its data to the input of *Network A*, whose outputs connect to the inputs of *Networks B and C*. A client may ask *Network A* for its outputs, but will it has no information about the *Devices*. The problem is similar to a client asking a DNS server for a name. If the server has no record information, either it will ask an affiliated server and act as a recursive middleman or directly reply with the affiliated server and let the client do the next iteration. To resolve the affected *Devices*, we augment *Processors* with a discovery and resource reservation protocol (RSVP) (Zhang, Deering, Estrin, Shenker, & Zappala, 1993). Using that protocol, clients can establish end-to-end channels with *Devices* regardless of the number, the location, and the graph structure of intermediate *Processors*. The proposed RSVP protocol states that:

- i. when a *Processor* receives an RSVP request it instantiates the abstract graph to a *Network* object and broadcasts the RSVP to all the output ports of the *Network*
- ii. the "leaf" *Processors* whose outputs do not link to other *Processors* or *Devices*, acknowledges the request and propagate backward an RSVP reply with its identifier
- iii. Once "root" *Processor* whose inputs do not connect to other *Processor*, receives RSVP replies from all its outputs, it establishes the channel
- iv. subsequent I/O requests traverse through the established channel as distinct streams.

4 Programmable Coordinators

In the previous Section we saw *Devices* for unifying various storage platforms and *I/O Processors* for in-transit processing. The combination of the two creates an end-to-end datapath for a client to send data to multiple *Devices*. The *Coordinators* are about synchronizing multiple clients sending data to multiple *Devices*.

4.1 Approach

Using composable drivers, the *Developers* can customize *Coordinator* semantics according to the application requirements, without direct input or any management from the application. Existing drivers serialize access to the log, monitor requests in real-time, and augment upper layers with access-pattern information. Next, we present a few of the challenges *Coordinators* are trying to address.

Service API	Comment
Load(Plugin) (Processor, error)	Load a datapath plugin
Processor.Discover() error	Discover the composite datapath
Processor.NewUpstream() (Upstream, error)	Spawn a new upstream network thread
Processor.NewDownstream() (Downstream, error)	Spawn a new downstream network thread
Graph Developer API	Comment
Up.Add(new(component), new(pname)) error	Add a new Kernel to the network
Up.Connect(pname, pname) error	Link Kernels
Up.Record(new(key), new(value)) error	Store state in a key-value map
Up.MapInPort(pname) error	Bind input port to a Kernel
Up.MapOutPort(pname) error	Bind output port to a Kernel
Application API	Comment
Up.SetInPort(new(channel)) error	Bind top-level channel to network port
Up.SetOutPort(new(channel)) error	Bind top-level channel to network port
Up.SetRuntime(env Environment) error	Environment for storing the state
Up.Init() error	Start running the network
Up.Wait() error	Wait until the network terminates

Table 2: A simplified version of the Processor API. For convenience to the reader, we omit some arguments.

4.1.1 Metadata Catalog

Coordinators provide a key-value database for cataloguing and discovery of logical files. Logical files do not contain data. A logical file is a view or representation of one or more physical files. Because *Coordinators* leverage existing databases to durably persist the catalogue, they serve similar purposes as the *Devices*. Every database is designed to address a different problem, with every problem family asking for a different combination of data structures and hardware. That includes Btrees for storage efficiency and high sequential throughput on hard disks (e.g., PostgreSQL); Btree+ for read-intensive workloads as they minimize I/O amplification and favour range iteration (e.g., LMDB, BoltDB (BoltDB, 2020)); or LSM for high insert volume as it leverages random-access of SSDs (L. Lu, Pillai, Gopalakrishnan, Arpaci-Dusseu, & Arpaci-Dusseu, 2017; Jain, 2017). Databases may also integrate optimizations for network-access (Y. Lu, Shu, Chen, & Li, 2017), or trade-off correctness (e.g., ACID) for concurrency (e.g., MVCC). Thereby, no database can perform optimally to all workloads. The best-fit selection depends on the application characteristics and the available hardware on the host.

4.1.2 Distributed Synchronization

Coordinators provide a set of distributed synchronization primitives that allows developers to focus on core application logic without worrying about the distributed nature of the application. This way, developers can decouple their applications from the semantics of particular data stores. Depending on the physical problem an application tries to solve, the *Coordinator* may be designed to opt for strict ordering and up-to-date information or stale information in favour of concurrency and scalability. The *Coordinator* framework provides a single API set for which an externally composed driver governs the semantics. Thereby, an application can switch from strong to relaxed consistency without changing the source code. The only call that must be hardcoded on the client-side is about acquiring access pattern information. More specifically, clients can ask *Coordinators* about the trends of a key (e.g., access frequency, most frequent client) to make intelligent data placement decisions. Nonetheless, such flexibility comes with the cost of an additional request over the network, which is not always needed.

4.2 API

The API supports two types of transactions: The *Update* and the *View*. The first is about allowing a client to write some changes to a top-level entity (e.g., a logical file), and the second is about reconstructing the data of a top-level entity on reading. In both cases, the client must open the respective type of transaction from the *Coordinator* and transfer data to or from the *Devices*. Notably, the *Coordinator* does not participate in the data transfer.

4.2.1 Update Transaction

The *Coordinators* are meant to perform access control of logical files when multiple clients want to access them. In order to achieve atomic completion of a distributed transaction, we apply a two-phase commit (2PC); an atomic commitment protocol that ensures that a transaction commit is implemented in the situation where a commit operation must break into two separate parts (Samaras, Britton, Citron, & Mohan, 1995).

When a client wants to write() to a logical file it must contact the *Coordinator* and ask to open an *Update* transaction. If successful, the client store data to collections on the *Devices*, named after the Transaction Identifier (TID). Figure 1 illustrates the process.

- **Commit-request phase:** the client asks the *Coordinator* to precommit information about the collections on the affected *Devices*, for the forthcoming operation. If commit is possible, *Coordinator* records the request to the intention log. Otherwise it directly rejects the request.
- **Commit phase:** at the end of data transfer, the client sends to the *Coordinator* a request with the metadata, asking to persist it. On commit(), the *Coordinator* appends the metadata as a record in the update log and atomically removes the record from the intention log. On abort() the *Coordinator* moves the entry from the intention log to a global garbage collection log. In case of a crash between the two phases, higher layers can query the intention log for the incomplete transaction, extract the affected *Devices*, and remove the partially written data.

Essentially, every *Update* transaction comprise a new version of the logical file. Doing so, enable developers to access particular changes in the logical file as to how they access particular versions on a revision control system (Table 3).

4.2.2 View Transactions

When a client wants to read() a segment of the logical file, it must contact the *Coordinator* and ask to open a *View* transaction. The returned transaction will include a copy of the “non-protected” records of the update log. “Non-Protected” means that there is no lock held for these records, and they can be modified by another transaction or removed by the garbage collector. The purpose of ‘non-protected’ records is to support informative purposes, such as calculating the file size. If the user client wishes to get a consistent view of the data, the *View* transaction can be opened with an optional lease. In such a case, the client must explicitly close the transaction for the lease to be released.

4.3 Record Masking

A critical difference between files and objects is that objects are immutable (write-once-read-many), whereas files are mutable (write-many-read-many). This difference is reflected in the management of the update log. For immutable entities, there is only a single entry in the update load, with is returned via the read() operation. In contrast, a file may be opened, written, closed, re-opened, written on a different offset, and closed against. Given that every write operation results in a new record being created, the reconstruction of a file may require the consolidation of multiple records.

To support both cases, our proposed solution is what we call “landmarks”. They are special entries in the log, used as instructions for the *Coordinator* to know how to reply to incoming requests. When a client opens a new *iew* transaction, the *Coordinator* iterates the update log backwards until it stumbles onto a landmark. It then parses the landmark and replies according to the instructions. We currently support *Ignor Previous* and *Disappear* landmarks. The former makes the *Coordinator* return immediately without going further backwards in the log — records located before the landmark become candidates for garbage collection. The latter makes the *Coordinator* respond as if there is no entry for the key. This landmark imitates a deletion operation without actually removing the data or losing track of it. The intention is to support snapshotting and versioning. I need the users can remove the landmark, and the data will become again available, e.g., to undo a remove operation.

Log Trimming Depending on the access pattern of the application, the update log can grow and impose delays on the requests. To avoid such a case, a background process on the *Orchestrator* periodically scans the log and move out-of-date versions to a global garbage collection log. Obsolete versions are those preceded by a landmark and do not participate in a protected *View* transaction.

Keyzone API	Return	Comments
Info(name string)	(Info, error)	Return key information
Create(Key, Reset)	error	Create a new or rim an existing log
Set(Key, Landmark)	error	Log-appended presentation instruction
BeginUpdate(Key, TID, Payload)	error	Append targets on intention log
EndUpdate(Key, TID, Payload)	error	Append version on update log
BeginView(Key, Filter)	([]Version, error)	Return versions for data reconstruction
EndView([]Version)	error	Remove versions locking (free to gc)

Table 3: Coordinator API. Every key describes a logical file as a tuple of an intention log and update log. In order to start writing a logical file, the clients must acquire an Update Transaction. Essentially, every *Update* transaction comprise a new version of the logical file; as a version on revision control systems. *BeginView()* traverses backward the update log until it finds a landmark. The landmark is an instruction as to how to reply

Figure 1: operation of the synchronous stack of the Coordinators. When a client starts a transaction, intentions (affected devices) are persistently stored in the intention log. The Coordinator does not interfere in the critical I/O (data)path between the client and the devices. When the client closes a transaction, the Coordinator persistently stores the transaction metadata in the update log - and remove the record from the intention log atomically. The demonstrated sequencer has a queue depth equal to 1. If there is a pending request, the queue rejects the rest. Because the stack is synchronous (the backend must confirm the operation before a handler replies), the client with the queued request may wait for an arbitrarily long time (we support leases and heartbeats).

References

- BoltDB. (2020). *An embedded key/value database for go*. Retrieved from <https://github.com/boltdb/bolt>
- Doxsey, C. (2016). *Introducing go. build reliable, scalable programs* (1st ed.). O'Reilly Media.
- Hildebrand, D., & Nisar, A. (2009). pNFS, POSIX, and MPI-IO: a tale of three semantics. *of the 4th Annual Workshop on*, 32–36. Retrieved from <http://portal.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=1713082> doi: 10.1145/1713072.1713082
- Jain, M. R. (2017). *Introducing badger: A fast key-value store written purely in go*. Retrieved 2010-09-30, from <https://blog.dgraph.io/post/badger/>
- jclouds, A. (2020). *The java multi-cloud toolkit*. Retrieved from <https://jclouds.apache.org/>
- Libcloud. (2020). *Python library which hides differences between different cloud provider api*. Retrieved from <https://libcloud.apache.org>
- Liskov, B., & Shrira, L. (1988). Promises: linguistic support for efficient asynchronous procedure calls in distributed systems. *ACM SIGPLAN Notices*, 23(7), 260–267. Retrieved from <http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=54016> doi: 10.1145/960116.54016
- Lu, L., Pillai, T. S., Gopalakrishnan, H., Arpaci-Dusseu, A. C., & Arpaci-Dusseu, R. H. (2017, March). Wisckey: Separating keys from values in ssd-conscious storage. *ACM Trans. Storage*, 13(1), 5:1–5:28. Retrieved from <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/3033273> doi: 10.1145/3033273

- Lu, Y., Shu, J., Chen, Y., & Li, T. (2017). Octopus: an RDMA-enabled Distributed Persistent Memory File System. *2017 {USENIX} Annual Technical Conference ({USENIX} {ATC} 17)*, 773–785. Retrieved from <https://www.usenix.org/conference/atc17/technical-sessions/presentation/lu>
- Morrison, J. P. (1978). Data stream linkage mechanism. *IBM Systems Journal*, 17(4), 383-408. doi: 10.1147/sj.174.0383
- NoFlow. (2020). *Noflo is a javascript implementation of flow-based programming (fbp)*. Retrieved from <https://noflojs.org>
- Petcu, D., Craciun, C., & Rak, M. (2011, 01). *Towards a cross platform cloud api - components for cloud federation*.
- Samaras, G., Britton, K., Citron, A., & Mohan, C. (1995, 10). Two-phase commit optimizations in a commercial distributed environment. *Distributed and Parallel Databases*, 3, 325-360. doi: 10.1007/BF01299677
- Shalom, N. (2020). *Aria and the 'least common denominator' problem of cloud portability*. Retrieved from <https://thenewstack.io/avoiding-least-common-denominator-approach-hybrid-clouds/>
- Sidelnik, A., Maleki, S., Chamberlain, B. L., Garzarán, M. J., & Padua, D. (2012). Performance portability with the chapel language. In *Proceedings of the 2012 ieee 26th international parallel and distributed processing symposium* (pp. 582–594). Washington, DC, USA: IEEE Computer Society. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/IPDPS.2012.60> doi: 10.1109/IPDPS.2012.60
- Stow. (2020). *Cloud storage abstraction package for go*. Retrieved from <https://github.com/graymeta/stow>
- Zhang, L., Deering, S., Estrin, D., Shenker, S., & Zappala, D. (1993). RSVP: A New Resource ReSerVation Protocol. *IEEE Network*, 7(5), 8–18. Retrieved from <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/lpdocs/epic03/wrapper.htm?arnumber=238150> doi: 10.1109/65.238150